

Progressive Crustal Deformation of Yinmabin Area and Its Environs, Mandalay Region

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Abstract

The present paper emphasized mainly on interpretations of deformation fabrics and stress field orientation related to progressive crustal deformation and deformation patterns of the Yinmabin area and its environs during India and Asia collision in Early Cenozoic time. On the basis of microfabric as well as in addition with megastructures, there are at least five types of structural deformation, which operated within the Shan scarp fault zone and Sagaing fault zone. The progressive structural deformation phases are compressional deformation, ductile extensional deformation, brittle-ductile extensional deformation, brittle extensional deformation and transpressional deformation.

Key words: deformation fabrics, microfabrics, progressive crustal deformation

Introduction

The Yinmabin area lies about 26 km, southeast of Thazi, Thazi Township, Mandalay Region. The study area, which lies more or less along the western margin of Southern Shan plateau and forming tectonically the Shan scarp region. Previous works are mainly based on the stratigraphy, petrology, regional geological studies and economic possibilities of the Yinmabin area and its surrounding region. Microstructures and related progressive deformation patterns however have not been studied in detail yet. In microscopic studies, mylonitic and deformed samples are used to determine the shear sense and deformation criteria observed on planes cutting parallel to the mineral grain elongation (lineation, XZ plane) and perpendicular to the mylonitic foliation (foliation, XY plane) where X, Y and Z are the principle axes of the finite strain ellipsoid ($X \geq Y \geq Z$).

Regional Geological Consideration

Regionally, most of the stratigraphic units together with granitoid plutons are in a general NNW-SSE structural trend. Precambrian to Paleozoic sequences raised topographic Shan Plateau and younger Tertiary sedimentary sequences. The Myanmar Central Basin in west with folded and faulted by Sagaing faulting. Mesozoic clastic sequences and Upper Paleozoic carbonate deposits were found overlying in associated with intrusion of granitoid plutons. Regionally, Mogok Metamorphic Belt starts from up country and pass over the study area in contact with Lebyin Group of Shan Plateau succession.

District Geology

The district geology of the Yinmabin area comprises the older granitoid plutons and Yinmabin metamorphics which belong to Mogok Metamorphic Belt. In the western part of Shan Plateau region, granitoid rocks are widely exposed along NNW-SSE trends, and these plutons belong to the Yinmabin-Payangazu granitoid plutons of Khin Zaw (1990). Two major episodes of granitoid intrusion occurred along the Shan Scarp region. The older granitoid rocks are slightly foliated, non-porphyrific or porphyritic, peraluminous and metaluminous, calc

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alkaline both I and S type, syn-orogenic granitoid rocks. (Khin Zaw, 1999; Than Than Myaing, 1986; Cobbing et al., 1992)

Brook and Snelling (1981) suggested that intrusive ages appear to range from late Cretaceous to Eocene. Rb/Sr age of 152 ± 24 Ma (Late Jurassic) was obtained for the Nyaungga granite, (northward 30 miles) of the Yinmabin area. K/Ar dates age from 55 to 82 Ma (Early Eocene-Late Cretaceous). G.I.A.C (1999) documented that the radiometric dating with K/Ar method indicates 62 ± 1.4 Ma on quartz and feldspar of foliated granite exposed at Yinmabin area, eastern part of Thazi site. Barley et al. (2003) documented that. Yebokson granodiorite yield U-Pb in zircon age of 120.92 ± 0.89 Ma (Early Cretaceous). According to these previous data and radiometric dating, the age of older intrusive rocks is in the range from Late Jurassic to Early Eocene. Initial intrusion probably occurred as early as Jurassic and the major episodes of intrusive activity emplaced during Late Cretaceous to Middle Paleocene.

Younger granitoid rocks are non-foliated, undeformed, medium-grained, non - porphyritic microgranite. These are formed post orogenic intrusive features with NNE-SSW trending. UNDP, DGSE (1977) have also mentioned out that the radiochronological studies of biotite from fine -grained biotite granite on the southern part of study area yielded an age of 24.5 ± 1 Ma. G.I.A.C. (1999) had been analyzed the biotite minerals from biotite microgranite at Thazi area, by Ar-Ar laser step-heating method. This reveals that the age of biotite microgranite is about 22.4 ± 0.9 Ma. According to these radiochronological data as well as in combination with regional consideration, biotite microgranite emplaced during post orogenic activity of Middle Miocene.

Metamorphic belt along the entire length of the western marginal Shan Plateau is distributed along NNW-SSE regional trend. Metamorphic rocks with foliated intrusive rocks of greenschist to lower amphibolites facies are exposed (Tin Tun Oo, 1980; Myat Thuzar Soe, 2000). Foliated intrusive rocks were mainly deformed by regional as well as local tectonic deformation events. Mg Thein (1972), mentioned these metamorphic units of Payangazu-Yinmabin area, informally named as Yinmabin Metamorphic units possessing low-grade metapelites, medium-grade meta-carbonate and high-grade quartzofeldspathic rocks, similar like Mogok Belt (Searle and Haq, 1964) along the entire western length of Shan Plateau.

There are at least two types of metamorphism involved, namely regional metamorphism and contact metamorphism. Clegg (1954) and Searle & Haq (1964) suggests that the regional metamorphism could be as young as Cenozoic. Bertrand et al. (2001) used Ar ³⁹/Ar ⁴⁰ radiochronological methods on high grade metamorphic rocks and foliated intrusive rocks have shown a major thermal event during Cenozoic time (Oligocene -Middle Miocene) and is related to northward migration of eastern Himalaya syntaxis. Development of contact metamorphism is evidenced by hornfelsic aureole at Yebokson area (Mitchell, 2002). The contact metamorphism is largely affected by forceful intrusion of Yinmabin-Payangazu granitoid plutons (Khin Zaw, 1990). The younger intrusion is characterized by emplacement of undeformed, medium grained biotite microgranite. Sedimentary and metasedimentary rocks, exposed around the study area are mainly Lower Carboniferous Leyin Group. Mesozoic clastic sequences and Upper Paleozoic Plateau Limestones are widely distributed in the eastern part of Yinmabin area.

The Structural Trends

Structural pattern of the area is largely dominated by NNW-SSE striking igneous and metamorphic belts. In eastern part, the strike or structural trends of the stratigraphic units varies from N 0° W to N 15° W. NNW-SSE trending en-echelon folded structure or fold axis orientation also follows the regional pattern. NE-WSW trending cross faults are mainly

exposed along the NNW-SSE trending major lineament zones, named here Pyinnyaung-Shan scarp fault zone. In westernmost part, microgranite exposures forming a regional strike along NNE-SSW direction.

Fault slip Analysis and Related Stress Field Orientation

According to the stress field analysis, stress field-1, that is characterized by maximum principal stress axis σ_1 E-W in orientation and stress field-2, that is typified by maximum principal stress axis σ_1 , NE-SW in orientation. Thrust faults are trending nearly N-S in position. Thrust planes are mostly evidenced at Pyinnyaung area and Yinmabin railway sections. Thrust planes are mostly evidenced at Pyinnyaung area and Yinmabin railway sections. Maximum principal stress (σ_1) related to the thrust slip displacement is probably oriented at about E-W in position. ENE-WSW trends of brittle normal faults across the older structures or fractures, stratigraphic trends and regional strike position. One major extensional brittle faulted feature is largely supported by detachment zone of upper crustal level, which is observed on metapelitic exposures of Yinmabin Metamorphics, along Yinmabin railway section. According to cross-cutting relationship of the fracture and fault traces from TM image, aerial photo interpretation and field criteria, the earlier stress position is typified by nearly E-W compressive stress axis and the younger stress position is typified by NE-SW compressive stress axis. See Fig (1,2)

Structural Deformation Features

According to analysis of fabric developments at each differential deformation style, the followings are concluded (see Table 1). Ductile extensional deformation is also marked by the development of mylonitic foliation, new grain development fabric, monocrystalline quartz ribbons, NNW-SSE to NW-SE stretching L-S tectonite fabrics and S/C fabrics that characterize the Yinmabin Metamorphics of Mogok Metamorphic Belt. C' fabric, mantled porphyroclasts, mica fish, antithetic offset grains and ataxial vein are mostly developed at middle crustal deformation or NW-SE orientation of brittle-ductile deformation zone. Oriented thin section studies indicate that these fabrics are deformed by NNW-SSE to NW-SE brittle-ductile extensional deformation, and previously ductilely deformed asymmetric boudins or well foliated, rigid porphyroclasts are cross cut by brittle fracturing with the development of ataxial vein or microdilational zone. Cataclastic or grain fragmentations are deformed at upper crustal deformation or brittle deformation zone. Fig (3, 4)

Fig (1) Map showing the stress, field patterns, the orientation of principal stress axes in the study area.

Fig (2) Fault slip criteria (A)Thrust related folded structure of metapsammitic rock,Yinmabin railway section. N 20°45.474', E 96° 17.320'; Facing : NW (B) Dextral strike-slip criteria on Plateau Limestones exposed along Pyinnyaung Shan Scarp fault; 20°49' 36.8"N 96° 24' 48.3"; Facing - NNE (C) Dextral strike-slip criteria on Plateau Limestones N 20°49'39.5'' & E 96°24'34.6' Facing - S (D) Extensional detachment criteria on metapelitic rocks exposed at Yinmabin area, Yinmabin railway section. N20° 46.083', E96° 17.553', Facing – E

Table 1.Fabrics development and progressive deformation through the continental crust of the area.

Assume : Geothermal Gradients 20°-25 °C/km (David and Reynold,1999)

Fig (3): A .Brittle–ductile extensional deformation represented by ataxial vein or stretched quartz fibre in mica schist .along Yinnabain railway section. Schistosity or foliation plane is along NNW-SSE direction, stretched quartz fibre is stretching along NW-SE direction in response to fluctuation in fluid pressure during simple shear, brittle-ductile extensional deformation, X.N. B.Photomicrograph of cataclastic texture, PPL. C. Ductile deformation represented by new grain development, X.N

Fig (4) Extensional deformation represented by microfabric features (X.N)(A) Micafish -Type II S/C tectonite, (B) Photomicrograph of σ_a type porphyroclast of feldspar in mylonitic gneiss (C) Composite shape fabrics represented by S/C fabrics in phyllite of the area exposed around Yinmabin railway section.(D) Ductile deformation represented by monocrystalline quartz ribbons, mylonitic quartzite, Yinmabin area (E)L-S tectonite fabrics in mylonitic quartzite, Yinmabin area (F) Antithetic grain scale faulting of rigid feldspar grain

Discussion and Conclusion on Tectonic Events

On the basis of the radiochronological data and structural deformation style in relation with Tertiary tectonics of Myanmar as well as in addition with the observed microtectonics, field structural data analysis and image interpretation, the structural and tectonic events of Yinmabin area and its environs are concluded .See Table 2

A time from Late Jurassic -Upper Cretaceous, the subduction of Tethys was active along the Sundaland or Indochina block active margin. In Yinmabin area, the diapiric injection of granitic materials is initially emplaced. Rb/Sr age (Cobbing *et.al*; 1972) of granite at Yebokson area also provided Late Jurassic age of granitoid intrusion. These granitic materials are known as older granitoid rocks or Yinmabin -Payangazu granitoids of Khin Zaw (1990).The continuous compression, derived from successive subduction of Tethy is observed to have crustal thickened by thrusting. In Yinmabin area, N-S trending, east directed thrusts are evidenced on Plateau Limestones of Pyinnyaung area and Yinmabin Metamorphics of Yinmabin railway section. Injection of granitoid pluton is still took place in response to E-W compressional deformation during Middle Paleocene. Pre-existing radiochronological data are also supported that the emplacement of granitoids intrusion was probably occurred until Middle Paleoceneand is known as older granitoid plutons or syn-kinematic Yinmabin-Payangazu granitoid plutons. The *lit-par-lit* injection of granitic material exposed at Payangazu, Kanabaw and Yebyu area is previously assigned as contact migmatite (Thein Zaw, 1980; Myat Thuzar Soe, 2000). These rocks are progressively deformed by increase in temperature and pressure due to regional compressive stress and forming medium-high grade metamorphic reaction of greenschist to lower amphibolite facies and locally known as Yinmabin Metamorphics. Radiometric dating also indicates that regional metamorphism along Mogok Metamorphic belt is initially occurred during Late Eocene (40 Ma). During Middle Paleocene-Late Eocene, the stress tensor is characterized by N-S trending σ_3 , orthogonal horizontal σ_1 and vertical σ_2 .

As the crustal thickening due to E-W maximum compressive stress was progressively developed, NNW-SSE to NW-SE simple shear, ductile extensional deformation is gradually dominated within the deeper crust. The maximum compressive stress is rotated ENE-WSW

and the development of crustal stretching is occurred along NNW-SSE to NW-SE direction. NNW-SSE trending ductile stretching deformation affecting the Yinmabin Metamorphics is not only evidenced by ductile structures, nearly ENE-WSW trending brittle normal faults are also observed. Exhumation of Yinmabin metamorphics core complex is partly controlled by brittle-ductile extensional deformation along NNW-SSE to NW-SE position.

At the late stage retrogressive deformation of the study area, brittle extensional deformation is characterized by ENE-WSW trending brittle normal faults and directly related to exhumation of Yinmabin Metamorphics. The evidence of detachment criteria exposed along Yinmabin railway section is the most extreme case of extensional deformation in crustal regions and it have also resulted the development of Yinmabin Metamorphics core complexes. Subsequent brittle normal structures are generated by a stress tensor characterized by NNW-SSE to NW-SE trending σ_3 , orthogonal σ_2 and vertical σ_1 . Active tectonic processes along the Shan Scarp region are not only characterized by N-S dextral shearing of Sagaing fault to the west but also characterized by N-S trending Pyinnaung Shan scarp fault to the east. Regional strike-slip structures were generated by a stress tensor characterized by NW-SE trending σ_1 , orthogonal horizontal σ_3 and vertical σ_2 . At the initiation of N-S shearing active dextral faults maximum compressive stress is rotated anticlockwise to nearly NE in position. In Yinmabin area, NW-SE trending en-echelon folded structures are also formed in metasedimentary of Lebyin Group and Mesozoic sedimentary units. These fold axes are oriented in oblique position to the N-S trending dextral strike-slip faults. Thus, the study area underwent transpressional deformation by the activation of N-S dextral shearing and NW-SE folding in en-echelon patterns resulting from the NE-SW compressional stress.

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Table – 2: Plate Tectonics Setting & Related Structural Deformation Features of Yinmabin Area & its Environs.

Tectonic Period	Structural & Tectonic Deformation	Stress Tensor & Stress Position	Plate Tectonic Setting	Block Diagram
Late Miocene- Plio Quaternary	Transpressional Deformation			
Late Eocene - Middle Miocene	NNW-SSE to NW-SE Extensional Deformation	<p>Brittle Extensional Deformation</p> <p>Brittle-Ductile Extensional Deformation</p> <p>Ductile Extensional Deformation</p>		
Middle Paleocene – Late Eocene	E-W Compressional Deformation			
Late Jurassic – Upper Cretaceous				